

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE CONTENT OF TEACHING TECHNICAL SCIENCES THROUGH VIRTUAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: This article is about the theoretical foundations of teaching technical subjects through virtual technologies. Today, we have achieved the ability to choose our own consumers in the global market and to present our diverse products at their true value.

Key words: Uzbekistan, Textile, Liverpool (England), Bremen (Germany), Consultative, Modern technology, linting, Continuous.

Uzbekistan is the main producer and supplier of cotton fiber, which is a raw material for textile and light industry products.

After our republic gained independence, a wide path to such opportunities was opened. Currently, we have managed to choose consumers on the world market and export our cotton at its real value. Cotton fiber sold abroad by our country is considered one of the main sources of revenue for its state budget.

Uzbekistan ranks fifth in the world in cotton fiber production and second in exports.

It should be noted that cotton fiber produced in our republic is exported to most countries of the world, including the USA, Greece, Russia, England, South Korea, Italy, Germany, the Netherlands, Japan, and others.

The Republic of Uzbekistan is a full member of international organizations such as the Liverpool (England), Bremen (Germany) and Gdansk (Poland) exchanges, as well as the International Cotton Consultative Committee. Therefore, the high quality indicators of cotton products produced by cotton ginning enterprises, meeting the requirements of world standards, and their demand in the world market are the main factors in the innovative development of cotton-textile clusters based on modern technologies, professional training in technical disciplines for future technical specialists.

In order to prepare and produce quality products, specialists in modern technical fields must have a deep understanding of the essence of the following work performed in cotton farms and the cotton ginning industry and have practical professional experience:

- cotton seeds grown on farms are collected from the fields and delivered to cotton processing points.
- where cotton seeds are received, they are prepared and stored, and then sent for primary processing.

The technology of primary processing of cotton includes the following main processes:

- drying of cotton with seeds;
- cleaning cotton with seeds from small and large impurities;
- ginning of cotton - separating fiber from seeds;
- linting of seeds - separating fluff from seeds;
- cleaning and pressing of fiber, fluff and fibrous waste, baling;
- preparation of seeds with seeds.

To carry out these processes, cotton ginning enterprises and cotton preparation points are equipped with the necessary technological machinery and equipment, a hydropress, transport, mechanization devices, sawmill repair and energy departments.

It is important to organize higher education in such modern enterprises in higher educational technologies and vocational training in technical disciplines based on cotton-textile clusters in higher educational institutions. In this process, the achievements of foreign and Uzbek scientists in certain fields of science, the experience of advanced enterprises, as well as their techniques and technologies, who have conducted scientific research in this area, were used.

In this process, there are improved requirements for vocational training in technical disciplines. The implementation of the unified education policy implemented in our country in the regions shows the need for effective development of innovative components of the higher education system and ensuring competitiveness in the market of educational services. In particular, today the creation of such a new mechanism in the pedagogical education system has become a vital necessity, which will ensure the modern and effective organization of education in higher education institutions, the satisfaction of interests as a result of ensuring competition, integration, coherence and continuity. Based on this important social significance of continuing education in the sustainable development of society, modern requirements, problems in the system and the fragmentation between science and education branches in solving them today determine the need to transfer continuing pedagogical education to a cluster development model.

A cluster is a form of integration of related enterprises, which allows to increase the competitiveness of the regional economy. In terms of organizational form, a cluster can be called a vertically integrated structure.

“Cotton-textile cluster” is a grandiose project that is one of the conditions for economic development. Getting to know it better and understanding its essence more deeply is important not only for industry professionals, specialists, economists, but also for the general public. Development requires innovation.

The role of the state in the formation of clusters plays an important role. In developed countries, some experience has been accumulated in the use of clusters in the formation and management of an innovative economy.

This strategy is widely used in European countries and the USA. Clusters are well developed in the UK, the Netherlands, Germany, the USA, Denmark, France, Italy, Finland, and India. Clusters completely occupy the industry of Denmark, Finland, and Sweden.

As the President of our country Sh.M. Mirziyoyev noted, it is advisable to create a cluster system in all sectors. Indeed, the creation of cluster systems in oil, gas, chemistry, biotechnology, pharmacy, informatics, automotive, transport logistics, food, education, fisheries, poultry farming, beekeeping, sericulture and other sectors will increase the volume of financing for scientific research and development, improve its quality, increase the level of technical support for scientific research work, create new opportunities for participation in external investment projects, training and advanced training of scientific and pedagogical personnel. In addition, in the cluster system, educational and scientific research centers will have ample opportunities and conditions for creating new scientific and methodological developments, testing them in a short time, more stimulating the work of employees and

specialists in production and scientific research, and inventing new goods with the Uzbek brand.

Also, scientific centers for training international cluster coordinators and Councils on cluster projects will appear in our country.

One of the most rational ways is that the issue of forming clusters in the textile and light industry system of Uzbekistan is being implemented not on a national scale, but on the basis of specific economic and social conditions in regions and provinces, based on the essence of cluster theory.

The cotton-textile cluster encompasses not only light industry, but also dozens of sectors, such as agriculture, the food industry, pharmaceuticals, and the production of construction products.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, it should be said that teaching technical subjects based on virtual technologies is very important today, because it is very important to create scientific areas by linking the innovative development of virtual technologies to the field of education and applying its essence to the whole society.

The implementation of the unified education policy implemented in our country in the regions shows the need for effective development of innovative components of the higher education system and ensuring competitiveness in the educational services market. A cluster is a form of integration of interconnected enterprises, which allows increasing the competitiveness of the regional economy.

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